

ON THE ROLE OF WATER CONTAINED IN THE SOLVENT USED IN FILTER PAPER CHROMATOGRAPHY. PART II

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The R_f values of the amino-acids with *n*-butyl alcohol-acetic acid-water, amyl alcohol-acetic acid-water and benzyl alcohol-acetic acid-water of varying compositions as developing solvents have been determined. R_f values are found to increase with the increase in water content of the systems. These three-component systems of suitable compositions have been found convenient for use as the second solvent for two-dimensional chromatography of the amino-acids.

In a previous communication (Burma and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 135), R_f values of the amino-acids obtained with isopropyl alcohol containing varying amounts of water have been reported. Miscible solvents, as isopropyl alcohol, have the advantage that their water-content can be easily chosen at any desired value. In case of partially miscible solvents, however, the water-content can be varied only within the saturation limit.

It has been observed that a medium water-content (say 30%) best serves the purposes of chromatography, but unfortunately, excepting one or two (phenol, collidine, etc.), all the partially miscible solvents take up comparatively much little water for their saturation. R_f values of the amino-acids developed with a solvent of low water-content are found to be very low and close to each other, thereby the solvent fails to resolve a mixture of them. The maximum amount of water taken up at 25° by butyl, amyl and benzyl alcohols are 20.27%, 9.8% and 10.8% respectively (International Critical Tables) and the maximum R_f values obtained with these solvents, saturated with water, are found to be 0.42 (of *nor*-leucine in case of *n*-butanol), 0.18 (of *nor*-leucine in case of amyl alcohol) and 0.33 (of phenylalanine in case of benzyl alcohol) respectively. Due to such low R_f values, the development with these solvents has to be carried out for long periods extending from one to three weeks (Miettinen and Virtanen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1949, 3, 459).

Many workers (Partridge, *Nature*, 1949, 164, 443; Hulm and Arthington, *ibid.*, 1950, 165, 716; Westall, *ibid.*, 1950, 165, 717; Reed, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1950, 183, 451; Pascu, Mora and Kent, *Science*, 1949, 110, 446) used these solvents for chromatography after addition of a third component, which is miscible with the solvents as well as water (e. g. pyridine in case of amyl alcohol, acetic acid in case of *n*-butanol, etc.). The object of the addition of the third component is obviously to increase the water content of the system. The effect of increased water-content of the three component systems on the R_f values of the amino-acids has been thoroughly studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The R_f values of the amino-acids with *n*-butyl, benzyl and amyl alcohols with the addition of various proportions of acetic acid as the third component were determined.

Owing to the high volatility of the solvents, ascending method of chromatography was followed (as described in Part I, *loc. cit.*).

The solvents were mixed up in measured volumes. The water-saturation capacity of the solvents in presence of a definite volume of acetic acid was determined roughly by observing the appearance of turbidity as increasing amounts of water were added. The water-content of the mixture, as used for chromatography, had always been less than that corresponding to the saturation capacity, so that lowering of temperature, if any, within reasonable limits did not bring about partial miscibility. The mixtures having the compositions used herein remained miscible down to about 20°.

R_f values of the amino-acids with various proportions of butyl alcohol, acetic acid and water are recorded in Table I. The amino-acids are arranged according to their

TABLE I

R_f values of amino-acids with n-butyl alcohol-acetic acid-water.
(Ascending chromatography)

Amino-acids.	BuOH sat. with water.	Comp. of the solvent mix. (butyl alcohol: acetic acid: water by vol.)					Upper layer of 4:1:1
		25:2.5:7.5	25:5:12.5	25:7.5:18.75	25:10:20	4:1:1	
Cystine*	0.01	0.03	0.16	0.26	0.33	0.04	0.07
Lysine*	.01	.04	.17	.33	.40	.10	.11
Asparagine	.01	.05	.18	.35	.40	.12	.11
Histidine	.02	.05	.20	.37	.43	.11	.13
Arginine*	.02	.07	.17	.38	.44	.14	.14
Aspartic acid	.01	.07	.17	.38	.45	.15	.16
Serine	.03	.10	.22	.38	.43	.18	.18
Glycine	.03	.10	.21	.38	.45	.17	.18
Glutamic acid	.03	.12	.24	.44	.50	.22	.21
Threonine	.04	.15	.27	.44	.48	.26	.21
Alanine	.06	.18	.30	.48	.51	.31	.25
Tyrosine*	.15	.32	.47	.60	.63	.42	.41
Methionine	.23	.36	.48	.60	.67	.52	.43
Valine	.22	.38	.49	.62	.68	.50	.47
Tryptophane	.23	.43	.48	.65	.71	.47	.50
<i>nor</i> -Valine	.30	.43	.55	.66	.71	.58	.52
Phenylalanine	.34	.52	.60	.71	.75	.62	.60
<i>iso</i> Leucine	.35	.54	.64	.73	.76	.66	.61
Leucine	.38	.54	.68	.75	.78	.67	.62
<i>nor</i> -Leucine	.42	.60	.68	.78	.80	.69	.68

*Applied as hydrochloride and neutralised with NH₃ vapour.

increasing R_f values. The second column shows the values obtained with butyl alcohol saturated with water. It has been reported that butyl alcohol, acetic acid and water, mixed in the proportion 4:1:1 (Reed, *loc. cit.*), and the upper layer obtained by mixing butyl alcohol, acetic acid and water in the proportion 4:1:5 (Partridge, *loc. cit.*), effect a good separation of the amino-acids from a mixture of them. R_f values obtained with these solvent mixtures are also recorded in the table for comparison.

Table II records the R_f values of the amino-acids obtained with various proportions of amyl alcohol, acetic acid and water and amyl alcohol saturated with water. In Table III are similarly presented the R_f values obtained with benzyl alcohol, acetic acid and water and benzyl alcohol saturated with water. As a small amount of esterification is possible on mixing benzyl alcohol with acetic acid, the mixture is allowed to stand for a few hours before use to allow the reaction, if any, to be completed. Higher proportions of acetic acid were avoided for this reason.

TABLE II

R_f values of amino-acids with amyl alcohol-acetic acid-water.
(Ascending chromatography)

Composition of the solvent mixture (amyl alcohol:acetic acid:water)

Amino-acids.	Amyl alcohol satd. with water.	Composition of the solvent mixture (amyl alcohol:acetic acid:water)				
		25:2.5:3	25:7.5:6	25:10:8.75	25:15:9	25:20:30
Cystine *	0	0	0.02	0.07	0.20	0.33
Lysine *	0	0	.05	.09	.26	.32
Histidine *	0	0	.05	.12	.31	.30
Arginine *	0	0	.06	.13	.33	.36
Asparagine	0	0.02	.09	.15	.26	.36
Aspartic acid	0	.02	.09	.15	.36	.41
Serine	0	.02	.11	.17	.31	.41
Glycine	0	.02	.11	.17	.31	.40
Glutamic acid	0	.03	.14	.19	.40	.47
Threonine	0	.04	.15	.21	.40	.48
Alanine	0	.05	.20	.26	.40	.50
Tyrosine *	0.04	.13	.28	.38	.55	.55
Methionine	.06	.17	.38	.43	.58	.58
Valine	.07	.18	.40	.46	.55	.58
Tryptophane	.07	.19	.42	.45	.63	.62
nor-Valine *	.07	.25	.44	.51	.61	.61
Phenylalanine	.15	.29	.50	.56	.65	.70
Iso-Leucine	.13	.33	.54	.60	.67	.73
Leucine	.15	.35	.56	.60	.68	.72
nor-Leucine	.18	.39	.59	.65	.69	.70

* Applied as hydrochloride and neutralised with NH_3 vapour.

TABLE III

R_f values of amino-acids with benzyl alcohol-acetic acid-water.
(Ascending chromatography)

Composition of the solvent mixture (benzyl alcohol : acetic acid : water)

Amino-acids.	Benzyl alcohol satd. with water.	Composition of the solvent mixture (benzyl alcohol : acetic acid : water)			
		25:2.5:4	25:5:6.5	25:7.5:10.25	25:10:15.5
Cystine*	0	0.01	0.07	0.15	0.24
Lysine *	0	.03	.10	.21	.33
Asparagine	0.01	.05	.12	.24	.34
Aspartic acid	0	.05	.12	.25	.35
Serine	0.02	.06	.15	.24	.35
Histidine *	.02	.04	.14	.26	.41
Glycine	0.02	.08	.16	.27	.38
Arginine *	0	.05	.16	.30	.43
Glutamic acid	0	.10	.18	.30	.38
Threonine	0.03	.14	.20	.32	.39
Alanine	.04	.26	.25	.35	.43
Tyrosine	.11	.32	.38	.49	.53
Valine	.13	.38	.46	.53	.57
<i>nor</i> -Valine	.17	.39	.50	.57	.60
Methionine	.20	.44	.49	.58	.61
Tryptophane	.23	.48	.53	.62	.66
<i>iso</i> Leucine	.25	.49	.58	.66	.68
Leucine	.27	.51	.59	.68	.69
<i>nor</i> -Leucine	.31	.51	.61	.69	.70
Phenylalanine	.33	.50	.60	.67	.68

* Applied as hydrochloride and neutralised with NH₃ vapour.

DISCUSSION

Of the three partially miscible alcohols, used in the present investigations, *n*-butyl alcohol has the highest water-content when saturated with water. This explains high *R_f* values obtained with this alcohol. With amyl alcohol having the least content of saturation-water, the rates are slowest.

The addition of acetic acid to the above alcohols increases their saturation capacity for water. Keeping the ratio of alcohols and acid the same, the *R_f* values of the amino-

acids vary according to the water-content of the three-component systems. If the amino-acids are arranged in order of their increased R_f values (as shown in the tables) the relative order practically remains the same with minor breaks in the sequence. Apparently the relative order of the solubilities of the amino-acids is not altered in the three-component systems, compared with that obtained with the same solvent in absence of acetic acid and containing a smaller amount of water.

In case of *n*-butyl alcohol saturated with water, most of the amino-acids have very low R_f values. With the addition of 2.5 c.c. of acetic acid to 25 c.c. of the alcohol and the corresponding increase of water-content to 7.5 c.c., the R_f values show a fair increase. The rate of increase decreases no doubt, but the R_f values gradually increase with the increase in water-content of the system. With higher water-contents, however, the R_f values become close to each other. The two types of composition that are generally used in the separation of the amino-acids (4:1:1 and the upper layer of 4:1:5) give almost identical values, thereby the composition of the two can be taken as identical for chromatographic purposes. The R_f values with these solvent mixtures are found to lie in most cases between those obtained with the 25:2.5:7.5 and 25:5:12.5 mixtures; although the water-content of the systems concerned is less than the both. This is due to the fact that the percentage of acid is much greater in those systems.

Amyl alcohol saturated with water is quite unsatisfactory for chromatography due to its very low water-content. The addition of even 7.5 c.c. of acetic acid to 25 c.c. of the alcohol does not improve the results much. With a still higher acid-content and a consequent increase in water-content, the desirable R_f values are obtained. The rate of increase of the sequence of amino-acids in the order of their R_f values are almost the same as in the case of butyl alcohol.

In the case of benzyl alcohol, however, the order of the R_f values shows some variation from what is observed with the other two alcohols. The aromatic character of the alcohol might be partially responsible for these variations. However, the gradual increase of R_f values and the decrease in the difference between the individual values with increase in water-content are, in general, almost the same in all the three alcohols.

It is interesting to observe, particularly with butyl and benzyl alcohols, that the R_f values obtained by addition of the same but low volume of acid to a definite volume of the alcohols, are close to each other than those at high acid-content. The high acid-content ensures high content of water. It is probable that in presence of considerable amount of water the difference in the hydroxylic nature of the solvents widens up leading to a greater difference in R_f values.

Extension to Two-dimensional Chromatography

Comparison of these R_f values with those obtained with phenol-water (Burma and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) indicate that any of these three alcohols containing suitable amount of acid and water may be used as a second solvent for two-dimensional chromatography, phenol-water being essentially the first solvent. Of the various compositions, however, 4:1:1 in the case of butyl alcohol, 25:10:8.75 in the case of amyl alcohol and 25:5:6.5 in

the case of benzyl alcohol are found to be the best compositions for the purpose. Benzyl alcohol-acetic acid-water has been extensively used by the author as the second solvent in two-dimensional chromatography of the free amino-acids present in leaves, roots and nodules of various plants.

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